

Effectiveness of Online Marketing

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Abstract

In the era of globalization, the internet plays a vital role in all spheres of life and industries. The Internet is very famous now adays for satisfying people with various services related to various fields. It is a very versatile facilities which help to complete many tasks easily and conveniently with few clicks. It can be any work of daily usage or any specific service which needs a lot of research and formalities to be done beforehand, as well as this marketing is not an exception either. Online marketing, which is also called internet marketing, involves the use of interactive, virtual spaces for the sake of promoting and selling goods and services. New synchronous, internet-based communication technologies contributed major economic sectors including marketing. Being cost-effective, flexible, and fast and enjoying an unprecedented global reach, internet marketing has brought about different businesses incredible gains. However, the new method also involves its special disadvantages, e.g., lack of personal contact, security and privacy etc . This paper deals with the effectiveness and pros and cons of online marketing. This continues with challenges such as problems of security, privacy, etc.

Keywords: Online marketing, customer behavior, marketing research.

Introduction

In the recent years, online marketing plays a vital role in the economy development of our country. Internet refers to the physical network that links computers across the globe. It consists of the infrastructure of network servers and wide area communication links between them that are used to hold and transport the vast amount of information on the internet. Introduction of the internet has reshaped the structure and performance of different sectors, e.g. hospitality, travel, health and medicine, marketing education etc. New trends of doing business online to attract customers to surf online to evaluate the services or products of an organization have lead organizations to use online marketing tools to deliver their messages to customers. The trend to market products online with a blend of online and off line strategies has produced success for companies that are using online marketing strategies to execute their business in the virtual business environment that has no boundaries. However, the concept of internet marketing merely does not full of advantages but some negatives appear alongside the advantages of internet marketing. Online marketing is a very powerful medium of advertising. It targets the correct audience and zones in promoting the business. The success of the business organization mainly depends upon the internet marketing. The online marketing agency takes care of all activities

for designing the website of business to implementing various marketing techniques including Internet marketing. Internet marketing will help to improve the business brand visibility, traffic and sales.

Importance of Online Marketing To Increase the Visibility of Business

These days everything can be done online by buying movie tickets to buying furniture for the home. The Internet has brought tremendous changes in our life style. Every business should recognize this and establish their presence on the internet. Internet marketing is beneficial for all the types of businesses. This will allow you to expand the visibility to a larger population.

To Connect with the Customers

Social media marketing allows connecting with the potential and returning customers. Update customers new or latest features of the business. To publicize the upcoming products or services and give a small description of these goods and services to customers. By doing this can attract new customers in the future.

Competition

These days people can access and purchase a wide range of goods online with the help of internet. It is very crucial for any business to maintain the competition against the small, local and large online retailers and businesses. This is possible only when the businesses make proper use of the internet marketing platform.

It is Good for Research and Development

It is good for research and development and it makes use of these keywords in the business to place the site on the top of the search engine results. Proper keyword usage allows driving potential traffic to the site. This is the best way to win new customers.

Legitimate Yourself

By establishing and maintaining the presence online, the business can show their customers that their business is active, dynamic and working to improve and is trying to grow. The Internet allows local businesses to legitimate themselves as successful companies. By this, they will be able to win and retain a large customer base. These days smart phones have become popular so, consider a simple application design which helps to download and keep the business at the forefront of the minds of people.

New Technologies

Online forms of communication provide more speed, versatility and structure. Advancements in technology have contributed to the rapid acceptance of the digital communication. Online marketing is executed in a variety of ways, including websites, content, blogging, social media and mobile.

Although traditional media is still highly relevant, technology has made the web more accessible. A company that sets up an online marketing strategy can keep up with technological advancements and tech-savvy competitors.

Cost Effective

Online marketing provides one of the most affordable ways for businesses to promote their products and services. It usually costs much less to set up a website and strengthen online presence with marketing strategies such as social media marketing in comparison to traditional marketing. It provides a cost-effective alternative to traditional marketing solutions. Social networking campaigns, for example, have the potential to send out marketing messages to several consumers at a much lower cost than an offline marketing campaign.

Tracking and Monitoring

Handling your marketing efforts online makes it easier to track and monitor progress. Instead of carrying out costly market research, real-time viewing of how your customers respond and measuring campaign success can help to work out the next strategy.

Wider Reach

- Including online marketing in your overall strategy gives you access to the high percentage of people who go online on a daily basis. A business that does not adopt the changing marketing environment will find it harder to thrive in the midst of online and socially savvy competitors.
- The internet has allowed businesses to have a wider reach on a global scale. The cost of using conventional or offline media typically restricts this level of reach with established businesses dominating traditional marketing.
- Online marketing opens new doors of opportunities for smaller businesses that have tighter budgets so that they can reach out to more customers around the world.
- Online marketing enables marketers to access their customers in a variety of ways while providing more products or services to them. As technology continues to advance, the ability to reach customers is likely to grow.

More Interaction

Conventional marketing techniques are associated with a one-way mode of spreading the message about brands while online marketing encourages interaction. Increased interactivity makes it possible for companies to get responses from consumers and be more adaptive. Database services are available to ease database management to get applications to market faster. Certified and skilled DBAs design infrastructure according to your requirements to ensure optimal performance of your applications. Specializing in various types of databases provides expertise and timely solutions. With expert database management, you will have more time for other functions that will improve your business.

Faster Impact

Online marketing can make a direct and faster impact. It makes it possible to move from viewing products to purchasing them quickly. With the click of a button can make bookings to try out products or order the latest device on the market. Such acquisitions can be made regardless of the time or location and enable business to function on a 24-hour basis. The internet speeds up the buying process and yields faster returns for businesses.

Increase Awareness and Convenience

Starting an online marketing campaign helps you increase awareness for a brand. While online, visiting sites and searching for products, customers get the chance to find you and what you offer.

More and more consumers prefer to make their purchases online. This is attributed to factors such as hectic schedules and the convenience of being able to get what need through online. A business owner needs to take advantage of the increase in online purchases by making it possible for customers to instantly access what they need.

Traffic and Sales

Using high-quality content or social networking as marketing techniques can drive more traffic to the site. An increase in the number of users who visit your site increases the prospect of sales. It also generates more interest in the business. Enabling the customers to buy what they want online instead of limiting them to being physically present at business premises will increase impulse purchases. This will boost profitability for business and make marketing efforts worthwhile.

Accessibility

Busy lifestyles can influence whether or not customers can go shopping within the usual business hours. Online marketing strategies give customers the option of going online to find what they need regardless of where they may be or what time it is.

Customized Strategies and Ongoing Communication

Marketing online enables companies to customize their messages according to the target market. The strategies help structure promotions in ways that will make the target audience receptive. Effective online marketing campaigns incorporate ways for consumers to keep in touch with the business. Through resources such as subscriptions, consumers can be kept aware of any new developments or products in the future after they make their purchases.

Types of Online Marketing Strategies

- Search Engine Optimization (SEO)
- Pay per Click (PPC)
- Social Media Advertising (Facebook, Twitter, Pinterest)
- Blogging
- Email or Newsletter Marketing
- Affiliate Marketing
- Banner Advertising
- Rich media ads – interactive media such as online video directories
- Online classified advertising
- Advertising networks

The sole purpose of effective online marketing is to utilize a strategy that has the lowest possible cost and risk investment, to maximize sales potential and receive a high return on investment (profit).

Advantages and Benefits of Online Marketing

Cost Effective: Advertising online offers one of the most cost-effective methods of marketing available in comparison with other mediums. Business owners can create, deliver and execute an online marketing campaign to a full spectrum of viewers, spending only what's necessary to reap maximum rewards later on.

Online marketing allows for statistics to be measured more effectively and easily and at a lower cost. Virtually all elements of an online marketing campaign can be traced and tested in some way. Tracking and measuring can be done almost instantaneously since online marketing encourages interaction by clicking on the ad and visiting the website, as well as other target actions.

Pay Per Click Advertising is notably the most effective means of generating immediate traffic, leads & sales to a website. Advantages of this form include only paying when a user clicks on your ad. The source of traffic can be easily tracked as well as identify which ads are achieving the best result in a campaign, and target an audience more specifically.

Online Marketing Campaigns can be Implemented much Faster than traditional forms of advertising, reaching a targeted audience within a matter of days and in some cases, hours.

Online marketing provides a greater flexibility level whereby campaigns can be altered to test new markets, evaluate new programmes and make changes more specific to a targeted market.

Search Engine Optimization (SEO) companies who specialize in helping companies best market their products and services online can successfully place them on the top or first page of major search engines and directories, such as Google, Bing and Yahoo.

Target Audience Closeness: Online advertising enables marketers to get close to a targeted audience and remain that way. Internet consumers are growing in numbers and staying online for longer periods. A complete marketing cycle from A to Z can be achieved with online marketing offering the opportunity to create an initial brand awareness right through to customer purchases. Since internet consumers are adapting their lives to suit a variety of elements available for them to do and use, online marketers, can capitalize on providing these opportunities.

A Successful Online Marketing Campaign

Tools that are necessary to deploy an effective online marketing campaign include:

Website: This is essentially a company's very first online marketing tool. Your website should be mobile friendly and easy to operate. Website addresses should be unique, simple, short, and memorable, as well as strongly reflect what a company stands for and intends to offer their target audience.

Landing Pages: is any web page you set up that's designed to prompt visitors to take a specific action.

Content: better content makes for a better website. Content should be packed with keywords that search engines can easily pick up on when a web user is online. Keywords in online marketing are truly a quality tool as this is what will draw a targeted audience onto your website.

New material and Updates: constant and consistent updates whereby new information is added will give your website content more bulk that has the added benefit of enticing viewers to return. Improvements will by no means go unnoticed by the public at large.

Marketing your Website: advertising your website on other websites advertising platforms such as Facebook Ads or using Google AdWords can greatly create more awareness of a company's brand, services or products.

Blogs: are fast becoming essential tools for online marketers as they can build a content-rich website, as well as attract targeted traffic from all major search engines. Other Things To Consider With Online Marketing

- Client testimonials are powerful in the way that they sell your product or service. Add these to your adverts or sites. Potential clients will gain more trust in your business if they can read your previous clients comments.
- Be sure to create an offer or promotion; potential clients always like something that ultimately solves their problem or provides them with a solution.
- Your website needs credibility for clients to trust you or your product and service. Take the necessary steps in obtaining a reputable site.
- Provide guarantees to your potential clients, offer 100% satisfaction or money back guarantee.

Disadvantages of Online Marketing

Internet Marketing Campaigns Can Be Copied

One of the dangers in Internet marketing is that a particular campaign can easily be copied by a competitor, and many have done so with utter disregard for the legal ramifications their actions may bring. Trademarks or logos can be used to defraud customers and take away a sizeable market share from you. Not only that, these can also be used for perpetrating negative and erroneous information about your brand, product or service that will ruin your online reputation – and lose valuable targeted customers.

Internet Marketing can Get Drowned by Too Much Online Ad Clutter

With both legitimate businesses and questionable entities like trolls, spammers and scammers present in the digital marketplace, the Internet is flooded with lots of online clutter. It would be doubly hard for Internet marketers to get noticed by their targeted customers. Some consumers now tend to simply ignore Internet advertising, making legitimate businesses lose valuable traffic and of course revenues in the process.

Internet Marketing Will Not be Taken Seriously if Not Done Professionally

Business owners and digital marketers should focus on bringing their Internet marketing campaigns to professional levels; otherwise, they will not be taken seriously by their targeted customers. First impressions matter whether you use traditional or Internet marketing and advertising channels so it would be to your greatest advantage to stay consistent and professional in whatever channel you are using for your campaigns.

Internet Marketing Involves Too Much Competition

Just like the proliferation of online ads, Internet marketing is faced with a great challenge of too much competition. Digital marketers are scrambling to get into a better position for optimum visibility for their marketing and advertising campaigns, and with the presence of too much competition, will make it doubly hard and expensive to get the attention of targeted audiences.

Internet Marketing Reputation Can Be Damaged by Negative Feedback

Internet Marketing Reputation Can Be Damaged by Negative Feedback Digital marketing tools are prone to their perennial problem of negative feedback which can damage your online reputation. A single post or tweet that defames or give erroneous claims and negative feedback about your products or services can scar and ruin your Internet reputation for a long time.

Conclusion

The Internet has revolutionized every aspect of life including economy and marketing. Internet marketing strategy is critical to the success of the business. Without, the new strategy in place, as well as clear-cut objective, will have a much more difficult time to stay on your path and realizing tremendous success at the end of that journey. The strategy doesn't necessarily need to be complex. Simpler will work better in a lot of cases. As the Internet continues to evolve, new technologies in Internet marketing will emerge and will define how products and services will be marketed shortly. Getting a better understanding of the power of Internet marketing by giving a comprehensive look at its advantages and disadvantages will prepare business owners and digital marketers in the years to come.

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